

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Fayzullayeva Muhayyo Rahmatillayevna

CULTURALLY MARKEDNESS OF STYLISTIC DEVICES

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

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